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Investigation of Primary School Teachers' Views on Undesirable Student Behaviors Encountered within the Frame of Classroom Management

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to determine undesirable student behaviors that primary school teachers encounter within the framework of classroom management and to determine their solutions to these undesirable student behaviors. In the research, descriptive survey model was used in accordance with the nature of qualitative research selected as the method. The research was carried out in the province of Aydın, Türkiye in the spring semester of the 2021-2022 Academic Year. The participants of the study, for which ethical conventions are followed, consist of a total of 12 primary school teachers, each of whom is represented by at least three primary school teachers from lower, middle and upper social economic levels. The selection of the study group was made with reference to the maximum diversity sampling, one of the sampling techniques. The opinions of the participants were collected with the help of a semi-structured interview form and the data obtained from the interviews were analyzed using content analysis method. In line with the data collected and analyzed by 2 researchers, the findings were shared within the scope of 6 themes. As a result, while it was determined that undesirable behaviors in classroom management were mostly caused by students, individual learning speed and friend relations, it was determined that these result from the factors pertaining to the environment, friends, technology use and family. Although the participants appeared to have various coping methods for undesirable behaviors, they stated that there exist responsibilities especially of parents, school staff and students in order to eliminate and minimize the relevant problems.

Keywords: Undesirable behavior, primary school teacher, classroom management, primary school, student.

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Introduction

In the most general sense, education can be described as the process of changing the behavior of an individual. At the end of the process, what is required from the individual is essentially the desired behavioral change; however, the process sometimes does not work as desired and undesirable behavioral acquisitions may occur in the individual with latent factors. In this context, it can be said that the function of education is not only the process of changing desired behavior, but also the task of eliminating, suppressing or extinguishing undesirable behaviors.

Considering that a large part of the education and training process takes place in the classroom, how well in-class education and training services work is related to the targeted product and output gains. The biggest goals of educators are to equip individuals in terms of knowledge, skills, values and academics in line with the program. There may be some factors that make the process impossible. These factors can be listed as management, physical facilities of the school, teacher, student, parent and environmental relations. When we examine these factors, it can be encountered as factors that can make the teaching of the lesson impossible, distract the attention of teachers and students, and make it impossible to conduct the lesson and activities. Charles (1999) mentions five types of undesirable student behavior on which teachers agree. These; aggressive behaviors, immoral behaviors, challenging the authority, interrupting the lesson, avoiding taking responsibility (Sadık, 2008). Korkmaz (2002) and Çelik (2003) state that four basic criteria are used while expressing undesirable behaviors and these criteria are; it is defined as the behavior that prevents the student from learning himself or his classmates, that the behavior endanger the safety of the student himself or his friends, that the behavior harms the school tools and equipment or the belongings of his friends, and that the behavior prevents the student from socializing with other students.

In line with the explanations above, any behavior that hinders educational efforts at school can be called undesirable behavior. Some of the undesirable behaviors have the greatest impact on the person doing the behavior; but some of them adversely affect the teacher, the lesson and the whole class. Undesirable behavior in the classroom; it disrupts the classroom order and actions, prevents reaching the goals, and causes especially the misuse of time resources (Başar, 2003). According to Martin and Pear (1992), undesirable behavior is expressed as the difference between the expectations of the teacher and the behavior of the students. For example, while teachers expect students to show interest and attention towards the lesson, students may want to sleep (Sadık, 2008).

In order for education to reach its goals, the foremost feature is expected to be the quality of the education and training process. However, a desired citizen can be raised with a qualified education. When talking about the quality of a school, what is really meant is how well it responds to the needs of students, the environment and society. The quality of the education service regarding the students is measured according to what level they have acquired the desired behaviors (Şentürk, 2010).

Undesirable behaviors in the classroom negatively affect the learning and teaching process, time management and classroom management. Undesirable behaviors in the classroom play an important role in the teacher's good organization of the teaching environment and in providing the content to the students. Good organization and maintenance of instruction also affects undesirable behaviors in the classroom.

In general, the causes of undesirable behaviors in the classroom are as follows; the inadequacy of the physical characteristics of the classroom, the way of giving responsibility to the students, the teacher's classroom management skills, the reasons arising from the students, the inconsistency of the teaching activities with the needs and interests of the students, the lack of planning of the teaching activities, the presence of students in the classroom who need special education with problems, the problems arising from the changes due to the developmental characteristics of the students, are related to each other (Ada and Ünal, 2000; Akçadağ, 2009; Ataman, 2005; Durukan and Öztürk, 2005; Korkmaz, 2002).

The school is not only a place where students are equipped with knowledge and skills, but also a place where students are prepared for real life. Primary school is also the first educational step where students encounter a new school, a new classroom, new friends and a new teacher after pre-school education. School, education, friend, teacher, value, skill, etc. the place where their image is formed is primary school. For this reason, in addition to the personal development stages of children during education, there is the acquisition of desired behaviors and the elimination of undesirable behaviors.

Whether a behavior is desirable or not depends on the individual exhibiting the behavior, the person or group, the environment, time, and cultural perceptions and characteristics (Gündüz and Konuk, 2016). For this reason, different characteristics related to undesirable behaviors can be encountered. However, in general, students' undesirable behaviors can be defined as behaviors that disturb other students in the classroom, disrupt the order of the classroom, do not comply with school and classroom rules, create chaos in the classroom environment and do not want the teacher. Behaviors that endanger security, damage to material goods, disrupt teaching, disrupt order and prevent socialization in the classroom are also examples of undesirable behaviors (Alkaş, 2010; Başar, 1999; Pala, 2005).

One of the most important problems encountered in classroom management for many years has been undesirable behaviors. Since these behaviors negatively affect education and training, researchers have studied every term. The solution of the problem requires a multidimensional and in-depth research; because the reasons for the emergence of undesirable behaviors are varied and complex (Erdem, 2010).

Undesirable behaviors are one of the most important problems that hinder social communication and teaching in the classroom. For this reason, it is important to focus on the subject, to determine the new undesirable behaviors that emerge with the changing conditions and to discuss what attitude teachers should adopt to such behaviors. Since this issue is directly related to classroom management, it is thought that it will help teachers to increase their awareness and success in classroom management.

When the literature in the field of classroom education and educational sciences is examined, it has been determined that many studies have been done. Undesirable student behaviors are aimed at primary school students (Çankaya and Çanakçı, 2011; Çetin, 2013; Sayın, 2001; Tolunay, 2008; Yüksel, 2005), towards secondary school students (Ekici and Ekici, 2014; Özdaş, 2013), and towards high school students (Siyez, 2009; Şenkulak, 2010; Yıldırım and Aydın, 2019), for higher education (Dönmez and Cömert, 2009; Sarıtaş, 2006), for teachers (Erdem, 2016; Çelikkakeli and Avcı, 2015; Girmen, Anılan, Şentürk and Öztürk, 2006; Gündoğdu, 2013; Medikoğlu and Dalaman, 2018; Memişoğlu, 2005; Özer, Bozkurt and Tuncay, 2014; Pala, 2005; Pehlivan, 2012; Tanhan and Şentürk, 2011; Yılmaz, 2008; Yumuşak and Balcı, 2018) and managers (Gökyer and Doğan, 2016; Parlakkaya, 2010; Şenay, 2011; Şenay, 2011). It can be said

that the studies carried out are mostly related to the detection of the presence of undesirable student behaviors and that these studies mainly involve teachers. When the literature is examined, it has been determined that although there are studies on the subject, concepts such as the detection of undesirable behaviors, the causes of undesirable behaviors and solutions are not included in the same study and studies for primary school students. In addition, considering that the studies conducted are mostly shaped around a qualitative paradigm, it is thought that the problems and solution proposals identified in each study may differ, and the study conducted with the thought that each study will deal with a separate situation and study group will also contribute to the field.

In this frame of reference, the aim of this study is to determine the undesirable student behaviors that primary school teachers encounter within the frame of classroom management and to determine their suggestions for undesirable student behaviors. In line with the purpose of the research, answers to the following questions were sought:

1. How do primary school teachers perceive undesirable student behaviors encountered whilst managing their classrooms?
2. What are the causes of undesirable student behaviors encountered in the classroom according to primary school teachers?
3. According to primary school teachers, how can technology be used to reduce undesirable behaviors in the classroom?
4. According to primary school teachers, what are the methods of coping with undesirable behaviors encountered in the classroom?
5. According to primary school teachers, what role can parents play in dealing with undesirable behaviors encountered in the classroom?
6. According to the primary school teachers, how are the solutions to the undesirable behaviors of the students?

Method

In this section, the research model, participants, data collection, data collection tool, data analyses, procedures for validity and reliability and ethics committee approval process analysis are explained.

Research Model

This study is a qualitative study designed in the descriptive survey model, which is a method (Creswell, 2016) that tries to give meaning by revealing the meanings attributed to social or human problems by groups or individuals. Within the scope of qualitative study, it is essential that the relationships between the methods used in observing, describing, and analyzing various dimensions of daily life are managed by the researcher (Dingwall and Miller, 1997).

According to Stewart and Cash, interviewing is a two-way and interactive communication process based on asking and answering questions, conducted for a predetermined and earnest purpose (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006). In the interview method, questions are set in advance and asked directly to the person (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006). In this research, which aims to explore the opinions of the primary school teachers involved in the research on undesirable student behaviors they encounter in classroom management, the descriptive survey model, one of the qualitative research methods, was preferred as part of the research to conduct.

Participants

The selection of the study group was made with reference to maximum variation sampling, one of the sampling techniques. The study group of the research consists of 12 primary school teachers, 4 of whom are teaching at each grade level, of 3 schools (lower-middle-upper) working in the province of Aydın, Türkiye in the 2021-2022 Academic Year. Demographic data of the study group are given in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Information on demographic characteristics of the participants

Participant Code	Gender	Age	Graduated School	Grade Level	Socio-Economic Level	Seniority Year	Institution Type
K1	M	47	Faculty of Education	2	Lower	25	Public School
K2	F	56	College	3	Lower	23	Public School
K3	F	56	College	3	Upper	30	Public School
K4	F	40	Faculty of Education	2	Middle	17	Public School
K5	M	46	Faculty of Education	4	Lower	22	Public School
K6	F	45	College	3	Middle	22	Public School
K7	M	55	Faculty of Education	2	Upper	13	Public School
K8	F	38	Faculty of Education	1	Upper	13	Public School
K9	F	45	Faculty of Education	4	Middle	19	Public School
K10	F	37	Faculty of Education	4	Upper	15	Public School
K11	F	34	Faculty of Education	1	Lower	13	Public School
K12	M	39	Faculty of Education	1	Middle	17	Public School

4 of the participants are male and 8 of them are female. Participants were selected equally from three different socio-economic (lower-middle-upper) levels and 3 participants represent each class level. In addition, all of the participants work in public schools, and 9 of them are graduates of education faculties and 3 of them are college graduates.

Data Collection

The data of this study, which aims to obtain the opinions of the primary school teachers about the undesirable behaviors seen in the students, the reasons for these behaviors, the methods used for the solution of the undesired behaviors and the solution proposal, were collected through a semi-structured interview form, which was finalized after the expert opinions. Interview is a very powerful method used to reveal people's perspectives, experiences, feelings, and perceptions (Bogdan and Biklen, 1992). As a result of the pilot applications, necessary arrangements were made, and the semi-structured interview form was determined as 7 questions.

The interviews were held in the teachers' room, in the administrators' rooms, in the school garden, at the participants' homes, by making an appointment with the participants. The interviews lasted an average of 35 minutes. Voice recordings were taken from the participants who gave permission for the interviews, and the data were recorded in the form of notetaking for those who did not give permission. After the interviews were completed, the audio recordings were transcribed. In order to check the accuracy of the data, the audio recordings were confirmed by an independent researcher.

Data Collection Tool

In this study, a semi-structured interview form was used as a data collection tool. Before the interview form was prepared, first of all, a literature review was conducted. Subsequently, an interview form was created by obtaining the opinions and approval of 2 faculty members from the ADU Basic Education Department, 1 faculty member from the Assessment and Evaluation Department, and 2 primary school teachers who completed their graduate education in the Classroom Education Program. In order to get the opinions of the participants about the undesirable student behaviors they encounter in the classroom management, to identify the problems they encounter and to determine the solution proposals, the interview form was piloted by interviewing one primary school teacher from different types of schools (lower-middle-higher) with different socioeconomic levels. As a result of the pilot application, some changes were made in the interview questions, and the changes made in the form were presented to the expert opinion again. Semi-structured interview form consisting of 7 questions, which was formed in line with expert opinions, was applied to a total of 12 participants from 3 different schools.

Analysis of Data

The data analyzes of the research were carried out in accordance with the content analysis technique, one of the qualitative research methods. Content analysis, first conceptualizing the collected data, then organizing it logically according to the emerging concepts and determining the theme that explains the data accordingly (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006); it is the process of defining, classifying, coding, and categorizing data (Hancock, 2002). Content analysis requires in-depth analysis of data and allows for uncovering themes that were not apparent before. The process performed in content analysis is to gather similar data within the framework of certain concepts and themes and to interpret them in a way that the reader can understand (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006). In this study, the analysis and interpretation of the data was carried out by the researcher as follows:

First of all, each interview form was coded as K1, K12... for teachers. The answers given to the questions in the interview form were meticulously examined by the researcher and coding was done with an inductive approach, adhering to the essence of the statements without a predetermined code content. While coding, attention was paid to determine the frequency of expression. The codes were brought together to examine their similarities and differences, and themes were formed by finding commonalities between similar codes. By reviewing the data, the codes and themes created by the researcher were compared, and the final version of the codes and themes were determined by referring to the expert opinion and defined in a language that the reader could understand.

All the data obtained during the interviews were analyzed independently by 2 researchers and the results were created. As a result of the content analysis, it was determined that the

percentage of agreement was 94%. In the presentation of the findings, some of the statements made by the participants individually are given. The data obtained were examined with cause-effect relationships and some judgments were reached (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006).

Procedures for Validity and Reliability

During the face-to-face interviews, it was tried to collect in-depth and real data by establishing closeness with the participants. In the study, besides the researcher himself, help was received from a different coder/faculty member working in the Department of Education Programs and Instruction at ADU. Direct quotations have been included to provide direct presentation of the data with a descriptive approach. Direct quotations were given regarding the findings in order to ensure the internal reliability of the research (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006). After 2 randomly selected interview forms were coded by the researcher himself and the other coder, the consistency between the analyzes was examined with the formula $(\text{agree}/\text{agree}+\text{disagree}) \times 100$ (Miles and Huberman, 1994). The agreement coefficient was calculated as .94 for the teacher interview form. These results were accepted as reliable for the research. In addition, the reliability was tried to be increased by giving codes between the teachers K1-K12 in the participants.

Ethics Committee Approval

The ethics application for the study was made on 07/04/2022 and the research was carried out with the approval of Aydın Adnan Menderes University Ethics Commission dated 26/05/2022 and numbered 2022/09.

Results

How the undesirable behaviors experienced in primary schools are interpreted by the primary school teachers, how they are perceived, what the problems are and what solutions are offered for these undesirable behaviors were tried to be revealed through the interviews, and content analysis was made in line with the data obtained from the interviews with the participants, and the findings were divided into different categories under 6 themes and expressed in codes.

Theme 1: Problems Encountered in Classroom Management

The list of codes, categories and frequencies extracted from the answers given to the questions asked to the teachers in order to reveal how the undesirable behaviors encountered by the primary school teachers in classroom management are perceived by the teachers are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Views of primary school teachers on the problems they encounter in classroom management

Theme	Category	Code	f
Problems Encountered in Management	School	Excess class size	1
		Lack of classroom equipment	1
	Teacher/Executive	Inconsistent behavior	1
		Speech without permission	6
	Blaming/complaining your friends	4	
	Defying directives	4	
	To lie	3	
	Irregularity	2	
	Come to school late	2	
	Damage to school	2	

Student		Stand up without permission	2
		Talk among themselves	1
		Go out without permission	1
		Deflecting the lesson from its goal	1
		Theft	1
Individual Speed of Learning		Distractibility	3
		Readiness of students	1
		Lack of motivation	1
		Pre/prerequisite learning	1
		Socio-economic level difference	1
Friend Relations		Abusive speech	3
		Slang/vulgar speech	3
		Damage your friends' belongings	3
		Disrespect	2
		Aggressive behavior	2
		Rudeness	1
		Making hand gestures	1
		Hitting each other	1
		Insult	1
		Inability to empathize	1
		Using your friends' stuff without permission	1
		Lack of affection	1
		Making fun of	1
		Division into groups	1
		Tease	1

In the statements of the teachers who participated in the interview, it is emphasized that more than one source in classroom management causes undesirable behavior and discipline problems. Many of the participants' state that they have problems with classroom management, albeit for different reasons. Problems in classroom management; reasons arising from the school, arising from the teacher and the administrator, arising from the student, arising from the individual learning speed of the students and the reasons arising from the friend relations of the students were evaluated in 5 categories.

An example of the opinions of teachers who stated that the reasons for undesired behaviors encountered in classroom management arising from the school are the excess of the class size and the inadequacy of the classroom equipment are as follows:

“The fact that the rules are not adopted in the classroom; I think that the high number of class students poses a problem in terms of classroom management and time management.” (K10)

An example of the opinions of the teachers who expressed the reason for the disciplinary problems experienced in classroom management stemming from the teachers and the administrators with the inconsistent behaviors of the teachers and administrators is as follows:

“...I think that the lack of consistent behavior by both teachers and administrators creates discipline problems in the classroom and causes problems for teachers to manage this process.” (K7)

Disciplinary problems in the classroom are caused by the student; it is explained by the concepts of " Speech without permission, blaming/complaining your friends, defying directives, to lie, irregularity, come to school late, damage to school, stand up without permission, talk among

themselves, go out without permission, deflecting the lesson from its goal theft". An example excerpt from a teacher's opinion on the subject is as follows:

"Being hyperactive in children leads to undesirable behaviors in the classroom. I can express them as some negative behaviors that can be encountered by behaving aggressively towards their friends, using their belongings without permission, damaging other people's belongings and classroom items, and scribbling on desks. In addition, behaviors such as speaking abusive, making gestures, coming to school late, not obeying the dress code, lying, stealing can be given as examples of some negative behaviors I encounter in classroom management." (K9)

It is stated that some of the disciplinary problems experienced in classroom management are caused by the differences in the individual learning speeds of the students. The factors affecting the individual learning speed of students are also expressed with concepts such as "Students' readiness, lack of motivation, pre/prerequisite learning, distraction and socio-economic level difference". An example excerpt from the teacher's opinion supporting this view is as follows:

"Children who learn faster in class than their other friends are more bored. He disturbs his friend next to him, pulls his friend's hair in front of and behind him, scribbles on the desk, tears up his friends' and his own notebooks, eats something in the classroom, and says he will not write in his writing studies. (K5)

It is stated that some discipline problems experienced in classroom management are caused by students' friend relations. The participants express the undesirable behaviors in the classroom arising from friendship relations with concepts such as "Abusive speech, slang/vulgar speech, damage your friends' belongings, disrespect, aggressive behavior, rudeness, making hand gestures, hitting each other, insult, inability to empathize, using your friends' stuff without permission, lack of affection, making fun of each other, division into groups and tease". An example excerpt from a teacher's opinion supporting this view is as follows:

"I think that with the digital age, children's communication skills are in trouble. We are faced with a generation that does not like to talk and read, who likes to listen even a little bit and gets bored quickly. For this reason, I try to analyze, manage, and evaluate my classroom management in line with the different developmental areas of children in proportion to the average age of the classroom." (K1)

Theme 2: Causes of Undesirable Behaviors Encountered in Classroom Management

The list of codes, categories and frequencies extracted from the answers given to the questions asked to the teachers in order to reveal how the causes of the undesirable behaviors encountered by the primary school teachers in classroom management are perceived by the teachers are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Primary school teachers' views on the causes of undesirable behaviors encountered in classroom management

Theme	Category	Code	f
Causes of Undesirable Behaviors Encountered in Classroom Management	Parent/Family	Low family education profile	3
		Presence of unconscious parents	3
		Possible wrong role models of parents	3
		Inconsistent parental behavior	2
		Living difficulties	2
		Indulging the parents	1
		Conflict between parents	1
		Negative attitude of parents to school	1
		Parents' only academic expectations	1
		The oppressive family model	1
		Negative parental suggestions	1
		Increase in the number of divorces	1
		Parents' perspectives on education	1
		Not spending quality time with children	1
		Environment/Friends	Being a role model
Peer bullying	2		
The desire for social acceptance and approval	2		
Blasphemy	1		
To lie	1		
Lack of empathy	1		
A lack of respect	1		
Selfishness	1		
Division into groups	1		
Reinforcing wrong behaviors	1		
Verbal violence	1		
Physical violence	1		
Wannabe	1		
Wrong choice of friend	1		
Use of Technology	Unconscious consumption of technology	5	
	Unconscious time consumption	5	
	Indifference of the parents	3	
	Parents' lack of control	3	
	Lack of control of technological channels	2	
	Being the wrong role model	2	
	Unconscious parents	2	
	Decreased confidence in the street	1	
The Other	Subconscious fears	1	
	Psychological problems	1	
	Character structure	1	
	Hormone and energizing foods	1	
	Child's past life	1	
	Developmental characteristics of the child	1	
	Physical factors	1	
	Inherited traits	1	
	Family attitude	1	
	Busy work life	1	
	Parents who are unfollowed and lacking in locus of control	1	

It is seen that primary school teachers explain the reasons for the disciplinary problems they encounter in classroom management as parents/family, environment/friends, use of technology and other reasons.

Some of the participants stated that the causes of disciplinary problems and undesirable behaviors in classroom management stem from parents/family. Participants express the undesired behaviors experienced in classroom management stemming from the parents/family with the concepts of “ Low family education profile, presence of unconscious parents, possible wrong role models of parents, inconsistent parental behavior, living difficulties, indulging the parents, conflict between parents, negative attitude of parents to school, parents' only academic expectations, the oppressive family model, negative parental suggestions, increase in the number of divorces, parents' perspectives on education and not spending quality time with children”. An example excerpt from a teacher's opinion supporting this view is as follows:

“The families are in the clear. In divorced families, the child goes to the mother and is praised there, then goes to the father and is praised. When this happens, it causes dissatisfaction in children. Uneducated families are also a big problem. Seminars given to teachers should actually be given to parents. In fact, it is necessary to take the children from the schools and bring the parents to the schools. Of course, it is very important at the academic level in families. There are also behavioral differences in children according to the education level of the family. There are differences between the behavior of children of primary school graduates and children of high school graduates. The second is the family's perspective on education. It affects whether the family sends the child to pre-school education. Behaviors of children with and without pre-school education. Be the best teacher as a teacher (although I don't know what a good teacher is) the child stays with us for 6 hours and spends the remaining 18 hours with his family. The child interacts more with his family. There is also the fact that if the child has willpower, the child is successful. Even in families with low academic success, the child can be successful if they are willing.” (K5).

Some of the participants' state that the discipline problems and undesirable behaviors in classroom management are caused by the environment/friends. Participants explain the reasons for the problems experienced in classroom management due to the environment/friends with concepts such as “Being a role model, peer bullying, the desire for social acceptance and approval, blasphemy, to lie, lack of empathy, a lack of respect, selfishness, division into groups, reinforcing wrong behaviors, verbal violence, physical violence, wannabe and wrong choice of friend.” An example excerpt from a teacher's opinion supporting this view is as follows:

“The reason for most undesirable behaviors in the classroom environment is that children imitate their other friends. When a deterrent sanction is not applied to a student's mistake, other children also apply it. I have students who see and practice behaviors such as swearing, lying, and standing up from their friends. These include female students. Children who exhibit positive behavior are more effective than negative ones. I have observed that children exhibiting this negative behavior put pressure on their other friends and create fear. Even the child that I said would never do it, I see, he starts exhibiting negative behaviors.” (K1)

Many of the participants stated that the discipline problems and undesirable behaviors in classroom management are caused by the use of technology. It is seen that the participants explained the reasons of undesirable behaviors experienced in classroom management with

technology, with concepts such as “Unconscious consumption of technology, unconscious time consumption, indifference of the parents, parents' lack of control, lack of control of technological channels, being the wrong role model, unconscious parents and decreased confidence in the street”. A sample quote from a teacher's opinion supporting these views is as follows:

“Television, tablet, computer, and phone shape children's behavior. Hit movies on television negatively affect children. They act like extraordinary characters. They imitate them. The games they play have a negative impact on the psychology of children. Students who spend more time in front of the computer are more antisocial. They're shutting themselves out. Their speech, discourse and behavior are similar to the game characters they play. These children also have trouble with writing. They misspell words. They act hastily. They have difficulty completing a sentence. They also become tired and sleepless. People no longer have time for children. For him, the parent directs the child to the television to the computer. There is no outside trust. But they don't know that using technology like this is very harmful to children.” (K1)

Some of the participants expressed the causes of disciplinary problems and undesirable behaviors in classroom management with other factors. It is seen that the participants who express the undesirable behaviors experienced in classroom management with other factors explain these factors with concepts such as “Subconscious fears, psychological problems, character structure, hormone and energizing foods, child's past life, developmental characteristics of the child, physical factors, inherited traits, family attitude, busy work life and parents who are unfollowed and lacking in locus of control”. A sample quote from a teacher's opinion supporting these views is as follows:

“The causes of undesirable behaviors in classroom management; psychological state of the child, previous events, inability to show the developmental characteristics of the period, physical factors, etc. I can list other reasons.” (K8)

Theme 3: Positive Use of Technology by Students

What can be done for primary school teachers to use technology positively by students? The list of codes, categories and frequencies extracted from the answers given to the questions asked to the teachers under the title of the question is given in Table 4.

Table. 4 Primary school teachers' views on students' positive use of technology

Theme	Category	Code	f
The Positive Use of Technology by Students	School	Physical and technological facilities of schools should be increased	2
		Lessons should appeal to more than one sense organ	1
		Technology consumption should be taught purposef	1
	Parent	Parents must restrain, supervise and watch	5
		Parents should be good role models in consumption	2
		Parents should spend quality time with their children	1
		Technological games should be supervised and educational	1
		Parents should be aware	1
		Programs should be appropriate for the development of children.	1
		Parents should be educated about technology and its consumption	1
Law/regulation	There should be legal sanctions and inspections	1	

Participants expressed their opinions by making suggestions about “School, parents and laws” about what should be done regarding the positive use of technology by students.

Participants think that with the positive use of technology by students, unwanted behaviors in school can be prevented. The participants made the following suggestions in order to prevent undesirable behaviors experienced in classroom education by using technology in a positive way. These are: “Physical and technological facilities of schools should be increased, lessons should appeal to more than one sense organ and technology consumption should be taught purposeful.” An example excerpt from a teacher's opinion supporting the above views is as follows:

“Technological tools are very inadequate in terms of visual and software used in schools. Their content is insufficient, many of them cannot be reached. Play-style things that will attract the attention of children and that they will enjoy can be presented to students in a way that they can be watched in the classroom. It is necessary to prevent it from being seen as something unattainable by children. It is necessary to prevent children from watching negative things. Children should not be confined to the house. There are also many foods that increase energy. They usually eat them. The breaks must be long; the schoolyard area is insufficient. There should be environments where children can move freely, swing, run and play, so that children can release their energy there. Even children who are talented in visual arts cannot develop in this area. There should be a visual arts teacher and a visual arts workshop so that children can be encouraged in these aspects so that they can get rid of the negative effects of technology.” (K1)

Participants talk about the points that parents should have in the positive use of technology by students. It is stated that parents should pay attention to the "Parents must restrain, supervise and watch, parents should be good role models in consumption, parents should spend quality time with their children, technological games should be supervised and educational, parents should be aware, programs should be appropriate for the development of children and parents should be educated about technology and its consumption" points in order to prevent undesirable behaviors in the classroom, at school or at home. A sample quote from a teacher's opinion supporting these views is as follows:

“Parents have a great role in gaining behavior and reducing or eliminating undesirable behaviors. A short-term reward can be placed after the desired behavior. It can make you watch a game or movie that your family has found and knows. It can enable the child to spend time in front of the computer and the phone in a controlled manner. He should definitely not leave the child alone with the computer or phone in his room or in another room. If he does, he should definitely go and check it every 15 minutes.” (K4)

Participants state that there are points that should be included in laws and regulations in the positive use of technology by students. An example excerpt from a teacher's opinion, which states that laws are more controlling and sanctionable, is as follows:

“As long as TV programs, internet usage, general broadcasts are not supervised by the authorities of the state, and unsuitable programs and channels are not sanctioned, their damage to society will continue.” (K11)

Theme 4: Methods of Coping with Undesirable Behaviors

The list of themes, codes and frequencies obtained from the opinions of primary school teachers on the methods of coping with the undesirable behaviors they encounter in classroom management is given in Table 5.

Table 5. Primary school teachers' views on coping with undesirable behaviors

Theme	Code	f
With Undesirable Behaviors Coping Methods	Suggestion	3
	Collaborating with family	3
	Pause	2
	Paying attention to individual learning speed	2
	Referral to the guidance service	2
	Operating the reward and punishment system	2
	Awareness raising	1
	Excitation	1
	Creating the rules together	1
	Solution together	1
	Teaching how to be solution oriented	1
	Teaching to be fair	1
	Don't ignore	1
	Dialogue and empathy	1
	Being consistent	1
	Finding the source of the problem	1
	Correct diagnosis	1
	Good detection	1
Right guidance	1	

It has been determined that the participants explained their opinions about what can be done and what should be done about the methods of coping with the undesirable behaviors they encounter in the classroom management with the concepts of "Suggestion, collaborating with family, pause, paying attention to individual learning speed, referral to the guidance service, operating the reward and punishment system, awareness raising, excitation, creating the rules together, solution together, teaching how to be solution oriented, teaching to be fair, don't ignore, dialogue and empathy, being consistent, finding the source of the problem, correct diagnosis, good detection and right guidance". An example quote from a teacher's opinion supporting these concepts is as follows:

“When there is a problem between friends, I want them to find a solution and talk first. If they can't find a solution, they come to me. I speak without taking sides. Then I send it to the guidance service. This way I solve many problems. In some cases, I also use the method of reward and punishment.” (K12)

Theme 5: Duties of Parents Regarding Undesirable Behaviors

The theme, code and frequency list indicating the opinions of the primary school teachers about the duties of the parents in coping with the undesirable behaviors they encounter in the classroom management are given in Table 6.

Table 6. Views of primary school teachers on parental duties regarding undesirable behaviors

Theme	Code	f
Duties of Parents Regarding Undesirable Behavior Problems	Parents must be consistent	4
	Parents should know their child well	3
	Parents should be good role models for their children	3
	Parents should spend good and quality time with their child	1
	Parents must be conscious	1
	Parents should identify the source of the problem well	1
	Parents and school should act together	1
	Should be in cooperation with the parent and the school	1
	Control at school should be left to the teacher	1
	Parents should always check and supervise their child	1

It is seen that the participants explained their views on the duties of parents in coping with undesirable behaviors with the concepts of “Parents must be consistent, parents should know their child well, parents should be good role models for their children, parents should spend good and quality time with their child, parents must be conscious, parents should identify the source of the problem well, parents and school should act together, should be in cooperation with the parent and the school, control at school should be left to the teacher and parents should always check and supervise their child”. An excerpt from a teacher's opinion supporting these views is as follows.

“Parents must accept their child's behavior. My child needs to get away from the notion that he can't do it. Unfortunately, that behavior does not improve when the parent does not recognize his child and does not accept that he can do that behavior. In fact, when the parent does not believe, the child constantly repeats that behavior and can reach the level of disrespect.” (K11)

Theme 6: Primary School Teachers' Solution Suggestions for Undesirable Behaviors

The list of themes, codes, categories, and frequencies indicating the solution suggestions of the primary school teachers participating in the interview for the undesirable behaviors seen in the students is given in Table 7.

Table 7. Primary school teachers' solution suggestions for undesirable student behaviors

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Code</i>	<i>f</i>
Solution Suggestions for Undesirable Behaviors in Students	Parent	Family-school should cooperate	5
		Family education should be given importance	2
		Child abuse should be prevented in the family	1
		Family should be good role model	1
	School	There should be an environment where children can release their energies	1
		There should be an environment where children can produce	1
		Psychological counselors should take charge instead of guidance teachers	1
		Subject teachers should attend arts and skills classes	
		Reward system should be used	1
		There should be break rooms	1
		Correct behavior should be immediately reinforced	1
		Guidance services should be provided to students by experts	1
		There should be sanctions	1
		Always keep in touch with children	1
		Be fair and consistent in the classroom environment	1
Rules should be clear and unambiguous	1		
“You” language should be preferred instead of “I” language	1		
	1		
Student	Children should be given responsibilities that they can do	1	
	Children should be supervised/supervised	1	
	Individual differences should always be considered	1	

Primary school teachers who participated in the interview state that parents, school and students have separate duties and assignments in terms of preventing, minimizing or even eliminating undesirable behaviors seen in students. The participants explain the missions for parents with the concepts of “Family and school should cooperate, family education should be given importance, child abuse should be prevented in the family and family should be good role model” in their proposals for solutions for undesirable behaviors. An excerpt from a teacher's opinion supporting this view is as follows:

“There should be close cooperation with families. Children are treated unfairly at home, they are beaten, children are pressured about success. Families should be consulted on these issues, necessary training should be given, and serious sanctions should be imposed on the parents of children who are exposed to beatings and slang words. The reward system for students who behave correctly should be implemented effectively.” (K5)

It is seen that the participants expressed the missions for the school with the concepts of “There should be an environment where children can release their energies, there should be an environment where children can produce, psychological counselors should take charge instead of

guidance teachers, subject teachers should attend arts and skills classes, reward system should be used, there should be break rooms, correct behavior should be immediately reinforced, guidance services should be provided to students by experts, there should be sanctions, always keep in touch with children, be fair and consistent in the classroom environment, rules should be clear and unambiguous and “you” language should be preferred instead of “I” language” in their suggestions for solutions to undesirable behaviors. The opinion of a teacher who supports this view is as follows:

“In schools, there should be an environment where children can throw their energies and produce new things. There should be sanctions for primary school students by the Ministry of National Education. There should be branching on the basis of courses. Specialized teachers should attend classes such as physical education, painting, and music. Psychological counselors and pedagogues should be appointed rather than guidance services in schools. In fact, they should always be present in such big schools. They should provide the necessary therapeutic support to the children. Family education should be given importance. Especially when some children's behaviors to the degree of illness are detected, trainings should be given to ensure that their families go through some education.” (K1)

It is seen that the participants explained the homework and duties of the students in the prevention of undesirable behaviors with the concepts of “Children should be given responsibilities that they can do, children should be supervised/supervised and individual differences should always be considered”. A sample quote from a teacher's opinion supporting these views is as follows:

“It is essential to make the student feel valued first. The source of the problem should be determined by knowing the student very well and analyzing it well. The child shows these behaviors, but whether he/she does it or is it the expression of different reasons, these should be analyzed very well. The problem should be solved by the counselors on the spot and on time before it gets too big. Collaboration should be made with the family. Students should be shown consistent and fair behavior in the classroom environment. It should not be ignored that each student has a different inner world. Individual differences should be taken into account. In terms of how both justice, consistency and individual difference will be at the same time, the student should be discussed and explained individually, again. Of course, they should be supported by the family. Problems that can be solved more easily with motivation in the classroom environment or by getting support from friends in a different way. The basis of all of these consists of correct determination and following the most correct way.” (K12)

Discussion and Conclusion

In this research, which was conducted with the aim of "examination of the views of primary school teachers about the undesirable student behaviors they encounter in classroom management", it is emphasized that there are undesirable behavior and discipline problems arising from the causes of more than one source in classroom management. It has been determined that the participants explained the behaviors that cause undesired student behaviors in the classroom with concepts such as " Excess class size, lack of classroom equipment, inconsistent behavior, speech without permission, blaming/complaining your friends, defying directives, to lie, irregularity, come to school late, damage to school, stand up without permission, talk among themselves, go out without permission, deflecting the lesson from its goal, theft, distractibility,

readiness of students, lack of motivation, pre/prerequisite learning, socio-economic level difference, abusive speech, slang/vulgar speech, damage your friends' belongings, disrespect, aggressive behavior, rudeness, making hand gestures, hitting each other, insult, inability to empathize, using your friends' stuff without permission, lack of affection, making fun of division into groups and tease". When the literature was examined, similar findings were found and as undesirable behaviors encountered by teachers in the classroom; disobeying classroom rules, abusive speech (Gürşimşek and Saygılı, 2008; Keleş, 2010), speaking without permission in class (Balay and Sağlam 2008; Elban, 2009; Şenay, 2011; Yıldız, 2006), shyness, hyperactivity and lack of attention (Yüksel, 2006), problems arising from watching violent programs on television (threatening), selfishness, hurting their friends (Dönmez and Çömert, 2009; Keskin 2009; Şenay, 2011), students trying to attract attention, high self-confidence, complaining about each other (Dönmez and Çömert, 2009; Kapucuoglu Tolunay, 2008; Neyişci Karakaş, 2005; Yüksel, 2006), students' eating whenever they want, habits from the kindergarten (singing and playing with play dough in the lesson), students' unwillingness to leave their families, parents' excessive devotion to their children, students' disrespect to the teacher (Çankaya and Çanakçı, 2011) and absenteeism (Dönmez and Çömert, 2009; Gürşimşek and Saygılı, 2008; Keleş, 2010; Neyişci Karakaş, 2005) has been spotted.

As for the reasons for the disciplinary problems encountered in classroom management, the participants indicated "Low family education profile, presence of unconscious parents, possible wrong role models of parents, inconsistent parental behavior, living difficulties, indulging the parents, conflict between parents, negative attitude of parents to school, parents' only academic expectations, the oppressive family model, negative parental suggestions, increase in the number of divorces, parents' perspectives on education, not spending quality time with children, being a role model, peer bullying, the desire for social acceptance and approval, blasphemy, to lie, lack of empathy, a lack of respect, selfishness, division into groups, reinforcing wrong behaviors, verbal violence, physical violence, wannabe, wrong choice of friend, unconscious consumption of technology, unconscious time consumption, indifference of the parents, parents' lack of control, lack of control of technological channel, being the wrong role model, unconscious parents, decreased confidence in the street, subconscious fears, psychological problems, character structure, hormone and energizing foods, child's past life, developmental characteristics of the child, physical factors, inherited traits, family attitude, busy work life, parents who are unfollowed and lacking in locus of control". When examined in the literature, similar findings were encountered. As Çelik (2003) stated; parents' beliefs, attitudes and behaviors, reward and punishment system, school disciplinary policies, students' beliefs, attitudes and expectations, school ethical rules, teacher's beliefs, attitudes and expectations, teacher's management style, social, cultural and economic factors, teaching techniques and methods, it has been determined that reasons such as the national program and physical environment are considered as undesirable behavior in classroom management.

When the categories of the concepts that cause undesirable behaviors are examined, it is seen that there are parents/family, environment/friends, technology use and other options. Due to the fact that the 21st century is the age of technology, the existing borders on the world have been removed and it has become possible to reach the desired information at any time. Online or written/printed resources have had their share of information pollution, and the groups that consume unconscious technology have been affected the most. In order to prevent this within the scope of the research, a great burden falls on schools, parents, the state (laws, regulations, judiciary, and other legal entities), especially for the positive use of technology. At school, teachers

want everyone to pay attention to " Physical and technological facilities of schools should be increased, Lessons should appeal to more than one sense organ, technology consumption should be taught purposeful, parents must restrain, supervise and watch, parents should be good role models in consumption, parents should spend quality time with their children, technological games should be supervised and educational, parents should be aware, programs should be appropriate for the development of children, parents should be educated about technology and its consumption and there should be legal sanctions and inspections" issues in order to reduce or eliminate the undesirable behaviors they encounter.

While the participants expressed the solution suggestions for the undesirable behaviors seen in the students with concepts such as "Family-school should cooperate, family education should be given importance, child abuse should be prevented in the family, family should be good role mode, there should be an environment where children can release their energies, there should be an environment where children can produce, psychological counselors should take charge instead of guidance teachers, subject teachers should attend arts and skills classes, reward system should be used, there should be break rooms, correct behavior should be immediately reinforced, guidance services should be provided to students by experts, there should be sanctions, always keep in touch with children, be fair and consistent in the classroom environment, rules should be clear and unambiguous, "You" language should be preferred instead of "I" language, children should be given responsibilities that they can do, children should be supervised/supervised and individual differences should always be considered" ,similar findings were also found in the literature. When the literature is examined, the suggestions for solutions regarding the undesirable behaviors that teachers encounter in the classroom; Expressed as "giving punishment and reward (Alkan, 2007; Çankaya and Çanakçı ,2011; Sipahioğlu, 2008), warning (Alkan, 2007; Kapucuoglu Tolunay, 2008; Yıldız, 2006; Yüksel, 2006), ignoring (Elban, 2009; Kapucuoglu Tolunay, 2008; Saritaş, 2006), be more sincere to students, integrate students with activities, guidance service (Kahraman, 2006; Keleş, 2010; Saritaş, 2006), assigning tasks (Çankaya and Çanakçı 2011; Kahraman, 2006), making students sit close to themselves , playing games, informing parents (Keleş, 2010), involving students in the lesson, explaining the importance of friendship, having activities, being understanding to students, giving place to current issues, listening to students, teaching the rule of eating at feeding time, playing games for children to get used to school, first allowing parents to come to school every week, raising awareness of parents and children about respect, communicating with parents, telling students that they should speak up, giving responsibility (Elban, 2009; Kapucuoglu Tolunay, 2008; Saritaş, 2006) and listening to students (Keskin, 2009)".

Suggestions

Although undesirable student behaviors in classroom management take place in the classroom, more than one factor has emerged that causes these undesirable behaviors. When these factors are examined, it has been determined that the factors that cause undesirable behaviors are caused by external factors (family, environment, technology and alike). Therefore,

- ✓ Primary school teachers should analyze the negative behaviors and unwanted student behaviors in the classroom,
- ✓ The causes of undesirable student behaviors in the classroom should be well analyzed,
- ✓ Parents, schools, and the environment should cooperate in order to reduce and eliminate undesirable student behaviors in the classroom,
- ✓ Incorrect use of technology, which is thought to cause undesirable student behaviors, should be turned into positive use,

- ✓ Primary school teachers should be directed to academic studies and trainings on classroom management,
- ✓ The duties and working styles of school guidance services should be reviewed,
- ✓ Parents should be educated on the subject through different trainings and meetings and awareness should be raised,

In addition, based on these results, the causes of undesired behaviors can be investigated in depth. Similar studies can be conducted in different provinces of our country. By doing mixed research and action studies on undesirable behaviors in the classroom, both in-depth research and more specific research can be done.

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